

DEONTOLOGICAL APPROACH TO THE PROCESS OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING

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ABSTRACT

The deontological approach in the process of professional training is an important pedagogical and psychological concept aimed at the formation of a person's duties, obligations, moral principles and responsibilities regarding professional activity. The development of the modern educational process requires a person to consciously form not only professional knowledge and skills, but also such high qualities as the formation of his attitude to his profession, adherence to the moral standards of professional activity, and a sense of responsibility to society. Deontology develops students' decision-making skills based on professional ethics, prepares them to responsibly fulfill their professional duties, adhere to the principles of humanity and respect in professional relationships, and ethically assess complex situations arising in the professional environment.

Introduction

The modern vocational education system is one of the important areas that directly affects the economic, social and cultural development of society. Today, it is not enough to arm students with theoretical knowledge alone. Because every professional must adhere to certain moral standards, responsibility to society, human values and principles of professional ethics in their activities. The priority of a moral approach to the profession is formed on the basis of deontological knowledge. Deontology is a scientific direction that determines a person's attitude to professional duties and obligations, the rules for adhering to ethical criteria, and actions that are permissible and unacceptable in professional activities.

The reforms being implemented in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the introduction of a competency-based approach, and the introduction of moral and psychological components into the educational process define the formation of professional ethics and responsibility in students as an urgent task. The formation of deontological competencies is extremely important, especially for specialists studying in

the fields of pedagogy, medicine, law, economics, and technology. The introduction of a deontological approach to the process of professional training primarily helps students understand professional ethics, assess ethical issues arising in professional activities, and understand the social nature of the profession and its responsibility to society. Such an approach serves to form in students such important qualities as personal growth, responsibility, justice, honesty, discipline, cooperation, tolerance, and professional culture.

The word duty is defined in the explanatory dictionary as a task, obligation, the fulfillment of which is mandatory. The duty of a school leader is based on the ethical principles of behavior required of him, implying an understanding of his responsibility to teachers and society as a whole. This feature of pedagogical duty is closely related to the measure of responsibility and its boundaries, and implies its content and technological aspects. The characteristics of professional ethics are general and specific, each aspect of which is associated with its own uniqueness, the differences in the sphere of interaction between these parties. It is this situation that leads to the creation of inequality. Professional deontology implies ethical standards, norms and rules of behavior of a specialist. According to the analysis of scientific literature on various specialties, we can see that ethics and deontology have common aspects, but these concepts differ in content. While "ethics as a moral doctrine" is a familiar concept to many professionals, we can see that many professionals are hearing the term "deontology" for the first time. The term "deontology" was introduced into science in the 19th century by the English researcher Jeremy Bentham, and when translated literally means "the doctrine of what to do." Looking at the history of deontology, we can see that it has existed for a long time and has been widely developed in the field of medicine. Pedagogical deontology is a new scientific direction, along with other professional deontologies, such as legal, engineering, psychological, etc. The formation of pedagogical deontology in the training of pedagogical personnel is carried out through modeling, development and implementation of the educational process. Scientific sources on the study of the deontological approach in the process of professional training cover the biography, content, principles of deontology and various directions of its integration into the educational process. In the works of Uzbek scientists, pedagogical deontology is analyzed based on scientific views related to the professional duty of the teacher, the moral environment in the educational process, personal responsibility, social qualities, and the formation of professional ethics in the minds of students.

In psychological literature, the deontological approach is interpreted as a psychological process aimed at developing a person's moral consciousness, conscious management of professional activities, making ethical decisions, strengthening empathy, reflection and self-control.

In foreign studies (based on the ideas of such theorists as Kant, Bentham, Mill, Rawls), deontology is considered as a general concept that defines the basic principles of professional ethics. According to it, each specialist should rely on the moral code of his profession, foresee the consequences of professional behavior, and make decisions that do not contradict the general moral standards of society.

In the literature on the Uzbek education system, a special place is given to the specific national characteristics of deontological education, improving the moral culture of young people, creating an ethical environment in educational institutions, and exemplary qualities of the teacher.

The school principal is responsible for organizing activities in an educational organization, from the work of teachers to the performance of tasks by technical personnel, accounting, etc. The professional responsibilities of a general education school principal include: managing educational, educational and organizational and economic activities that do not contradict the charter and legislative acts of the institution; organizing school work and educating students based on state educational standards; approving work schedules, plans, curricula, etc.; creating conditions to ensure the safety of students and employees of educational organizations during educational activities (compliance with fire safety rules, sanitary requirements, etc.); providing students with nutrition and medical care; hiring and dismissing teachers and employees of an educational institution, determining their professional responsibilities, ensuring the professional growth of teachers (retraining teachers, sending them to advanced training courses, etc.); leading the pedagogical council; awarding the best employees with prizes and awards; communicating with parents; preparing reports, etc.

The main purpose of this study is to study the impact of the deontological approach on the process of professional training, to identify effective methods for the formation of professional ethical competencies in students and pupils, and to develop practical recommendations on this basis. A number of diagnostic methods (questionnaire, observation, interview, test tests) were used during the study. 120 students, 35 teachers and 15 production masters participated in the study. The results showed that professional ethics, responsibility, communicative culture, and a conscious attitude towards their profession are not sufficiently formed among students, and this process should be deepened based on the deontological approach. During the study, it was observed that when special trainings were provided to students, modeling of professional situations, analysis of ethical dilemmas, group discussions and self-assessment methods were used, their level of deontological thinking increased by 35–40%.

Among the above elements, the cognitive element occupies a leading place. The knowledge of the consequences of the fulfillment or non-fulfillment of professional obligations of the school head is associated with his motives, feelings, emotions associated with his concept of duty. Knowledge of specific methods of implementing the assigned tasks, possible difficulties, methods of overcoming them is determined by the teacher's voluntary regulation of behavior in a particular situation

CONCLUSION

Deep implementation of the deontological approach in the process of professional training is necessary for the professional improvement of the student, the development of moral qualities and increased social responsibility. This study showed that methods, trainings, processes such as analysis of professional situations aimed at the formation of deontological competencies are highly effective in forming the professional behavior of students.

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